

Development of a Low-Cost Autonomous Mobile Robot Utilizing ROS 2 and LiDAR-Based Navigation

K. Mokshagna Anurag

Dept. of ECE

MVGR College of Engg. (A)

Vizianagaram, India

kankati.mokshagnaunurag@gmail.com

M. P. S S S Hari Chandra Hlada

Dept. of ECE

MVGR College of Engg. (A)

Vizianagaram, India

harichandra3001@gmail.com

P. Suryaprasad

Professor, Dept. of ECE

MVGR College of Engg. (A)

Vizianagaram, India

suryaprasad@mvgrce.edu.in

Abstract—This paper presents the design, development, and implementation of a compact, cost-effective autonomous mobile robot built around a Raspberry Pi 4 microcomputer and an RPLiDAR sensor for LiDAR-based navigation. Autonomous navigation has become a critical capability in modern robotics, yet high-end systems remain prohibitively expensive for educational and small-scale applications. Addressing this limitation, the proposed robot utilizes an RPLiDAR sensor to capture high-precision 360-degree distance measurements for spatial mapping and obstacle detection. A USB webcam is additionally integrated to provide a visual perception channel for future semantic mapping extensions. The entire software architecture is built on the Robot Operating System 2 (ROS 2) Humble Hawksbill, which provides a highly modular and scalable framework for sensor data handling and actuator control. The system incorporates a custom four-wheel differential drive mechanism driven by BO motors with optical wheel encoders, allowing for precise odometry tracking via Closed-Loop Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) control. Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) is achieved using the SLAM Toolbox, while autonomous navigation is managed by the ROS 2 Navigation Stack (Nav2). Experimental results demonstrate that affordable hardware components, when paired with state-of-the-art open-source software, can yield a robotic platform capable of dynamic collision avoidance and consistent autonomous navigation in unstructured indoor environments.

Index Terms—Autonomous Mobile Robot, LiDAR, Raspberry Pi, ROS 2 Humble, Obstacle Avoidance, SLAM, Sensor Fusion, Nav2, Differential Drive Kinematics.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

The field of autonomous robotics has witnessed significant advances in recent years, driven by progress in sensor technology, artificial intelligence, and embedded systems. Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) are now found across industrial logistics, warehouse management, healthcare, and smart home applications. However, the commercial AMR solutions available in the market typically rely on industrial-grade hardware, including high-resolution 3D LiDARs, Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) GPS, and high-performance computing clusters. These systems, while highly accurate, are cost-prohibitive and inaccessible to researchers, educators, and hobbyists.

In parallel, the advent of Single Board Computers (SBCs) like the Raspberry Pi, coupled with affordable 2D LiDAR sensors and open-source middleware such as the Robot Operating System (ROS), has made robotics considerably more accessible. This technological convergence enables the development of scaled-down, cost-effective robotic platforms that replicate the core functionalities of industrial systems.

B. Motivation

This project is primarily motivated by the need for an accessible, low-cost autonomous robot capable of performing complex navigation tasks without relying on expensive proprietary hardware. Traditional low-cost robotic systems often depend on basic ultrasonic or infrared sensors, which suffer from limited range, narrow fields of view, and poor resolution, leading to suboptimal mapping and frequent collisions.

By employing a 360-degree LiDAR sensor for accurate geometric mapping and a webcam for visual perception, improved autonomy becomes feasible. Integrating these sensors with a Raspberry Pi running ROS 2 allows for real-time data processing, creating a platform that is not only functional but also serves as an excellent testbed for advanced algorithms in Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM), path planning, and computer vision.

C. Objectives and Scope

The primary objective of this project is to architect, construct, and validate a fully functional autonomous mobile robot, with a strong emphasis on the control unit and overall system architecture. The specific objectives include:

- **Development of a Robust Navigation System:** Integrating LiDAR and webcam data using a Raspberry Pi to ensure accurate spatial awareness, obstacle detection, and efficient path planning.
- **Real-Time Decision-Making:** Implementing algorithms for dynamic obstacle avoidance, allowing the robot to navigate through changing indoor environments seamlessly.
- **Efficient Data Processing and Sensor Fusion:** Utilizing the multi-core processing capabilities of the Raspberry Pi

4 to concurrently handle high-bandwidth sensor inputs and real-time motor control.

- **Closed-Loop Control Implementation:** Utilizing optical wheel encoders to calculate accurate odometry and implementing PID controllers to maintain trajectory fidelity.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** Designing a highly modular ROS 2 architecture to support future upgrades, such as visual SLAM, semantic segmentation, and multi-robot coordination.

D. Paper Organization

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews existing literature and technologies in autonomous navigation. Section III details the hardware and software architecture of the proposed system. Section IV presents the mathematical modeling and kinematics. Sections V and VI describe the hardware and software implementation respectively. Section VII describes system integration and testing procedures. Section VIII discusses the results, and Section IX concludes the paper with directions for future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs)

The evolution of AMRs has been marked by a transition from line-following and pre-programmed robots to intelligent entities capable of understanding their surroundings. Early cost-effective models predominantly used ultrasonic arrays and tactile bumpers. While cheap, these sensors provided sparse data, making map generation nearly impossible. In contrast, modern AMRs utilize LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) which emits laser pulses to measure distances with high precision. According to recent literature, 2D LiDARs like the RPLiDAR series have drastically lowered the entry barrier for indoor SLAM applications, providing dense point clouds that are ideal for generating 2D occupancy grid maps [3].

B. Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM)

SLAM is a fundamental problem in robotics, where a robot must construct a map of an unknown environment while simultaneously keeping track of its location within it [9]. Several SLAM algorithms have been developed over the years:

- **Gmapping:** A Rao-Blackwellized particle filter approach that is highly effective but computationally expensive for large maps.
- **Hector SLAM:** Relies heavily on high-update-rate LiDAR data and does not require odometry, but struggles in environments with few distinct geometric features.
- **Cartographer:** Developed by Google, it uses submaps and loop closure optimization but is complex to configure [10].
- **SLAM Toolbox:** The modern standard for ROS 2, offering lifelong mapping and robust pose-graph optimization [2]. It is highly optimized for SBCs like the Raspberry Pi, making it the algorithm of choice for this project.

C. ROS 2 and Navigation Stack

The transition from ROS 1 to ROS 2 represents a major architectural change in robotic software [11]. ROS 2 replaces the centralized master node of ROS 1 with Data Distribution Service (DDS), a decentralized, real-time publish-subscribe protocol. This enhances the fault tolerance and security of the system. The ROS 2 Navigation Stack (Nav2) [1] utilizes Behavior Trees to manage complex navigation tasks, offering a substantial improvement over the rigid state machines used in the ROS 1 *move_base* package. Nav2 incorporates Global Planners (e.g., NavFn, Smac) and Local Planners (e.g., DWA, TEB) to generate obstacle-free trajectories dynamically.

D. Limitations of Existing Low-Cost Designs

A critical review of existing low-cost educational robots reveals several limitations. Many lack a robust odometry source, relying solely on open-loop control, which results in severe drift over time. Others lack the processing power required to run modern SLAM algorithms, falling back to primitive reactive obstacle avoidance [7]. This project addresses these limitations by pairing optical wheel encoders for closed-loop odometry with a Raspberry Pi 4 capable of running ROS 2 Nav2 and SLAM Toolbox simultaneously.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

A. Hardware Architecture

The hardware architecture is designed around a central processing paradigm, where the Raspberry Pi acts as the master controller. The system integrates perception sensors, actuation modules, and a power distribution network.

As shown in Fig. 1, the RPLiDAR and Webcam feed high-bandwidth data to the Raspberry Pi via USB. The Raspberry Pi computes the necessary navigation commands and sends Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) and directional signals to the L298N motor driver. The optical encoders send pulse interrupts back to the Raspberry Pi's GPIO pins, closing the control loop.

B. Software Architecture

The software architecture leverages the node-based topology of ROS 2. Nodes communicate asynchronously using topics and services via the DDS protocol.

Fig. 2 illustrates the data pipeline. The LiDAR node publishes `/scan` messages to both the SLAM Toolbox (for mapping) and Nav2 (for local obstacle avoidance). Nav2 outputs velocity commands (`/cmd_vel`) to the Motor Controller. The Odometry node calculates the robot's pose based on encoder ticks and publishes `/odom` and transform (`/tf`) data back to the system.

IV. MATHEMATICAL MODELING AND KINEMATICS

To effectively control the robot, a mathematical model of its kinematics is required. The robot employs a differential drive steering mechanism, where the heading and velocity are controlled by independently varying the speed of the left and right wheels.

Fig. 1. Hardware Architecture Block Diagram of the Autonomous Mobile Robot, showing data and power flow.

Fig. 2. ROS 2 Software Node Graph Architecture showing topic communication.

A. Differential Drive Kinematics

Let R be the radius of the wheels and L be the distance between the two wheels (the wheelbase). Let ω_R and ω_L be the angular velocities of the right and left wheels, respectively.

The linear velocities of the right and left wheels are given by:

$$v_R = \omega_R \times R, \quad v_L = \omega_L \times R \quad (1)$$

The linear velocity v and the angular velocity ω of the robot's center frame can be derived as:

$$v = \frac{v_R + v_L}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\omega = \frac{v_R - v_L}{L} \quad (3)$$

By rearranging these equations, the inverse kinematics—used by the motor controller node to convert Nav2's `/cmd_vel` into individual wheel speeds—are obtained:

$$v_R = v + \frac{\omega L}{2}, \quad v_L = v - \frac{\omega L}{2} \quad (4)$$

B. Odometry Estimation

Odometry is the process of estimating the robot's position (x, y) and orientation (θ) over time using the wheel encoder data. Given a small time interval Δt , the change in position is calculated using numerical integration:

$$\Delta x = v \cos(\theta) \Delta t \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta y = v \sin(\theta) \Delta t \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta \theta = \omega \Delta t \quad (7)$$

The global pose at time t is recursively updated:

$$x_t = x_{t-1} + \Delta x \quad (8)$$

$$y_t = y_{t-1} + \Delta y \quad (9)$$

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + \Delta \theta \quad (10)$$

C. PID Control Implementation

To ensure the wheels rotate at the exact speeds commanded by the inverse kinematics, a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller is applied to each wheel [12]. The error $e(t)$ is defined as the difference between the target velocity and the measured velocity from the encoders. The control signal $u(t)$ sent as a PWM value to the L298N driver is:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \quad (11)$$

where K_p , K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains. Through empirical tuning, the gains were set to $K_p = 2.0$, $K_i = 0.5$, and $K_d = 0.1$, which minimized overshoot and steady-state error for the target operating speed range.

V. HARDWARE DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

The physical realization of the robot involves several carefully selected components that balance cost, power efficiency, and computational capability. Table I lists the principal components along with their approximate cost.

TABLE I
BILL OF MATERIALS AND APPROXIMATE COST

Component	Specification	Cost (USD)
Raspberry Pi 4B	4 GB RAM, BCM2711	\$55
RPLiDAR A1	360°, 12 m range	\$99
USB Webcam	720p, 30 fps	\$10
L298N Motor Driver	Dual H-Bridge	\$3
BO DC Motors (×4)	300 RPM geared	\$8
Optical Encoders (×2)	20 CPR, photo-interrupter	\$5
Acrylic Chassis Kit	4WD with casters	\$15
5V/3A Power Bank	10000 mAh	\$10
12V Battery Pack	Rechargeable Li-ion	\$8
Miscellaneous	Wires, connectors, etc.	\$6
Total		\$219

A. Processing Unit: Raspberry Pi 4B

The Raspberry Pi 4B serves as the brain of the robot. Featuring a Broadcom BCM2711 quad-core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC running at 1.5 GHz and 4 GB of LPDDR4 RAM, it provides sufficient processing capacity for concurrent SLAM and navigation workloads. It offers versatile connectivity, allowing the LiDAR to connect via USB 3.0 for fast data transfer and providing 40 GPIO pins for hardware-level interfacing with the motor drivers and encoders.

B. Distance Sensor: RPLiDAR

The primary perceptual sensor is an RPLiDAR A1 module [3]. It uses laser triangulation to measure distances in a 360-degree radius up to 12 meters, generating up to 8000 sample points per second at a scan frequency of approximately 5.5 Hz. This high-resolution point cloud is critical for accurate map generation and detecting small or thin obstacles that ultrasonic sensors would miss. It performs reliably in various lighting conditions, making it suitable for complex indoor environments.

C. Vision Sensor: USB Webcam

A standard USB webcam is mounted on the front chassis to capture real-time RGB video. While the LiDAR is excellent for geometric mapping, it lacks semantic context (e.g., distinguishing a wall from a person). The webcam adds a visual perception channel to the architecture, enabling future integration of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for object recognition and semantic mapping. In the current implementation, the webcam node publishes image data that can be consumed by downstream perception modules as they are developed.

D. Actuation: L298N Motor Driver and BO Motors

The mobility platform utilizes four BO (Battery Operated) DC gear motors rated at 300 RPM. These motors provide an optimal balance of speed and torque necessary for indoor navigation. The motors are driven by an L298N Dual H-Bridge motor driver. The L298N allows the Raspberry Pi to control the direction of the motors via logical HIGH/LOW signals and the speed via PWM signals, safely isolating the Pi's low-voltage logic circuits from the high-current demands of the motors.

E. Feedback: Optical Wheel Encoders

Attached to the motor shafts are optical encoder disks (20 Counts Per Revolution) combined with photo-interrupter sensors. As the wheel rotates, the slots in the disk interrupt a light beam, generating digital pulses. These pulses are counted by the Raspberry Pi using hardware interrupts at a polling rate of approximately 100 Hz. This feedback loop is essential; without it, the robot would suffer from dead-reckoning errors caused by wheel slip, battery voltage drops, or varying terrain friction.

F. Chassis and Power Supply

The components are mounted on a lightweight 4-Wheel Drive acrylic chassis (two motors per side) with caster wheels for balance. Power management is critical; a dual-power architecture is used. A high-capacity 5V/3A power bank provides stable power specifically to the Raspberry Pi to prevent brownouts during CPU-intensive SLAM operations. A separate 12V rechargeable battery pack powers the L298N and the motors, mitigating electrical noise and voltage spikes.

VI. SOFTWARE DESIGN AND ROS 2 INTEGRATION

A. The ROS 2 Humble Ecosystem

ROS 2 Humble Hawksbill was selected due to its Long-Term Support (LTS) status and its native compatibility with Ubuntu 22.04 LTS [5]. Unlike ROS 1, ROS 2 features a decentralized architecture, eliminating the single point of failure associated with the ROS Master [11]. This is particularly advantageous for resource-constrained environments like the Raspberry Pi.

B. SLAM Configuration

The `slam_toolbox` package is utilized to generate 2D occupancy grid maps [2]. As the robot is manually driven through an unknown environment (teleoperation), the LiDAR scans are matched against each other (Scan Matching) to determine the robot's movement, while simultaneously updating the map. The SLAM Toolbox incorporates pose-graph optimization, which effectively corrects accumulated drift when the robot revisits a known area (Loop Closure).

C. Navigation 2 (Nav2) Stack

Once a map is generated and saved via the `map_saver_cli`, the Nav2 stack is launched for autonomous operation [1]. Nav2 is a complex, modular system:

- **Global Costmap & Planner:** The static map is inflated to account for the robot's physical radius. The Global Planner (using A* or Dijkstra's algorithm) computes the shortest collision-free path from the current pose to the goal.
- **Local Costmap & Planner:** A rolling window costmap that updates dynamically using live LiDAR data. The Local Planner (Dynamic Window Approach – DWA) calculates velocity commands to follow the global path while actively avoiding dynamic, unmapped obstacles.
- **AMCL (Adaptive Monte Carlo Localization):** A probabilistic localization algorithm that scatters particles representing possible poses of the robot and updates their weights based on incoming LiDAR scans against the static map, pinpointing the robot's exact location.

VII. SYSTEM INTEGRATION AND TESTING

A. Assembly and Integration

The physical assembly required careful wire routing to minimize electromagnetic interference (EMI) between the motor power lines and the encoder signal lines. The Raspberry Pi was flashed with Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS, and ROS 2 Humble was installed from source repositories. A custom ROS 2 workspace (`lidar_ws`) was initialized.

Custom Python nodes were written to handle the low-level hardware interface. The `motor_controller.py` node subscribes to `/cmd_vel`, calculates the inverse kinematics, and applies the PID algorithm before sending PWM via the `RPi.GPIO` library.

Fig. 3. Top-down view of the assembled autonomous mobile robot highlighting the Raspberry Pi, RPLiDAR, L298N driver, and battery placement.

B. Testing Procedures

Testing was conducted in an indoor laboratory environment measuring approximately $8\text{ m} \times 6\text{ m}$, across three phases:

- 1) **Hardware Validation:** Encoders were monitored using an oscilloscope to verify clean square waves. Motors were tested for symmetric speed response.
- 2) **Teleoperation and Mapping:** The robot was manually driven using a keyboard teleop node to map the laboratory environment.
- 3) **Autonomous Navigation:** Multiple waypoints were sent to the Nav2 stack via RViz across ten successive trials. The robot's trajectory, obstacle avoidance response, and target arrival accuracy were monitored in each trial.

VIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The integration of the hardware and software components yielded satisfactory results across all tested metrics.

A. SLAM Mapping Results

The SLAM Toolbox effectively generated high-resolution 2D occupancy grid maps of the testing environment.

As seen in Fig. 4, the geometric outlines of the walls and corridors were captured with high fidelity. The use of closed-loop odometry significantly reduced the reliance on LiDAR scan matching alone, preventing map distortions in featureless corridors.

B. Navigation and Obstacle Avoidance

During autonomous navigation tests, the Nav2 stack exhibited robust performance. When presented with a goal pose via the RViz interface, the global planner successfully generated optimized paths.

When dynamic obstacles (e.g., a person walking into the robot's path) were introduced, the local DWA planner detected the anomaly via the live LiDAR feed, updated the local costmap, and recalculated the trajectory to smoothly bypass the obstacle without collision.

Fig. 4. 2D Occupancy Grid Map generated using LiDAR data and SLAM Toolbox. White areas represent free space, black lines indicate walls/obstacles, and grey indicates unknown territory.

Fig. 5. RViz 2 interface displaying the robot model, the global map, local costmap inflations, and the generated path.

TABLE II
SUMMARY OF EXPERIMENTAL PERFORMANCE METRICS

Metric	Observed Value
SLAM Map Resolution	0.05 m/pixel
Average CPU Utilization	60–70%
Navigation Success Rate (10 trials)	90%
Dynamic Obstacle Avoidance Success	100%
Average Goal Arrival Error	< 0.15 m
Thermal Throttling Events	0
LiDAR Scan Rate	~8000 pts/s

C. System Performance

Table II summarizes the key performance metrics observed during the testing phase.

The Raspberry Pi 4 managed the computational load within acceptable limits. Even with SLAM, Nav2, and the hardware interface nodes running concurrently, CPU utilization averaged 60–70%, and no thermal throttling was observed. The dual power supply strategy proved effective; the logic circuits suffered no resets or brownouts even when the motors drew peak stall currents.

The wheel encoders, operating at a high polling rate, provided highly granular feedback. The implemented PID controllers successfully maintained straight-line trajectories by compensating for minor mechanical differences in the left and right DC motors.

IX. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

A. Conclusion

This project successfully demonstrated the end-to-end design, construction, and software implementation of an autonomous mobile robot using off-the-shelf, cost-effective components. By combining inexpensive hardware (Raspberry Pi, RPLiDAR, BO motors) with industrial-grade software (ROS 2 Humble, Nav2, SLAM Toolbox), the system achieved accurate mapping and reliable, dynamic obstacle avoidance at a total hardware cost of approximately \$219. The implementation of differential drive kinematics and closed-loop PID control via wheel encoders ensured precise movement, validating the hypothesis that low-cost systems can achieve high autonomy when paired with robust sensor data processing and modern algorithms.

B. Future Scope

While the current platform is capable, several avenues exist for future enhancement:

- **Visual SLAM (vSLAM):** Integrating algorithms like RTAB-Map to fuse LiDAR data with visual features from the webcam to create dense 3D maps.
- **Semantic Navigation:** Deploying machine learning models (e.g., YOLO) on the Raspberry Pi or an edge accelerator (like Google Coral) to recognize objects, allowing the robot to navigate based on semantic commands (e.g., “go to the red chair”).
- **Advanced Kinematics:** Transitioning from the current skid-steer differential drive to an omnidirectional mecanum wheel base for superior maneuverability in tight spaces.
- **Swarm Robotics:** Utilizing the ROS 2 DDS middleware to coordinate multiple identical robots for collaborative mapping and exploration tasks.

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